

The Dielectric Constant of Binary Mixtures. Part I. Halides of Methylene and Ethylidene in Benzene.

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In a recent paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 673) it has been shown from the measurement of the temperature-sensitivity of *D.E.K.* by the heterodyne null-method that the dipole moment of methylene bromide is greater than that of methylene chloride and a still greater dipole moment in the case of methylene iodide has been predicted on the basis of the molecular model tentatively suggested therein, treating the electric moment (dipole moment) as a vector quantity. The measurement in the case of methylene iodide could not be taken up by the aforesaid method owing to some technical difficulties such as dissociation at high temperatures and the low vapour pressure of the compound. Hence another method, *i.e.*, the modified Nernst bridge method has been developed to measure the dipole moment of methylene iodide. It is also interesting to undertake the measurements in the case of ethylidene halides to see whether the dipole moments of these compounds follow the same law as that of the methylene halides. It might be pointed out in this connection that in the notice of the *Proc. Roy. Soc.* meeting held on the 21st February, 1929, Hartshorn and Oliver has also adopted the capacity method for the accurate determination of *D.E.K.* of liquids in which they claim an accuracy of 1 in 10,000 approaching therefore results obtained by the heterodyne null-method.

The idea of molecular polarisation as introduced by Debye (*"Handbuch der Radiologie,"* 1925, 6, 625) has made it possible to calculate the dipole moment of the molecules of a substance from their dielectric constant and density measurements provided they are dissolved in a solvent which has no dipole moment. Non-polar liquids such as carbon tetrachloride, carbon bisulphide, pentane, hexane and benzene are suitable solvents of this type. Thus if a binary mixture consists of a polar liquid (1) obeying Debye law and a non-polar liquid (2) obeying Clausius-Mosotti law, then at a definite temperature the general additive law of polarisation should be satisfied

for different concentrations if the molecules of the two liquids do not react upon one another. Hence the molecular polarisation of such a binary mixture is given by

$$P_{12} = \frac{\epsilon - 1}{\epsilon + 2} \cdot \frac{M_1 C_1 + M_2 C_2}{d_{12}} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$= P_1 C_1 + P_2 C_2 \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\therefore P_1 = \frac{P_{12} - P_2 C_2}{C_1} \quad \dots (3)$$

where ϵ = dielectric constant of the mixture having density d_{12} at the room temperature.

M_1, M_2 = molecular weights of the solute and solvent respectively.

C_1, C_2 = molecular fractions " " "

P_1, P_2 = molecular polarisation " " "

But according to Debye, for a polar molecule, $P_1 = P_1'' + P_1'$ (where P_1'' known as the optical part is due to distortion and P_1' is due to orientation).

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore P_1 &= \frac{4\pi N}{3} v_1 + \frac{4\pi N}{3} \cdot \frac{\mu^2}{3KT} \\ &= \frac{\epsilon_1 - 1}{\epsilon_1 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d_1} + 20 \cdot 71 \times 10^{26} \mu^2 \\ &= \frac{n_1^2 - 1}{n_1^2 + 2} \cdot \frac{M}{d_1} + 20 \cdot 71 \times 10^{26} \mu^2 \quad \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

where

N = Avogadro number ($6 \cdot 06 \times 10^{23}$);

v_1 = Molecular polarisability;

μ = Dipole moment;

K = Boltzmann constant ($1 \cdot 37 \times 10^{-16}$);

T = Absolute temperature (298°);

ϵ_1, n_1, d_1 = Dielectric constant, refractive index and density respectively of the polar liquid at the room temperature.

Hence combining equations (3) and (4), the dipole moment, μ , of the solute molecule can be calculated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the modified Nernst bridge method the necessary condition of silence in the telephone, which is used as a detector, is secured when the leads from the telephone are connected to points which should not only be at the same potential but where the potential, *i.e.*, the alternating *E.M.F.* should be at the same phase. Since the phase angle depends on the resistance, inductance and capacitance in the arms, a balance of resistance and inductance is therefore required along with a balance of capacitance. This is obtained by the simultaneous adjustment of capacitance and resistance in the proper arm of the bridge. Hence determination of the capacitance is made as if the resistances were not there.

The frequency of the alternating *E. M. F.* was 1000. The Magnanini solution was used for the variable resistance for a sharp detection of the null-point. The apparatus was well earthed.

The experimental condenser was of parallel plate type. It was first carefully calibrated by using benzene, ethyl ether and octane. The capacity (C_0) was thus found to be $36.32\mu\mu F$. The variable standard condenser used was the same as described in a previous paper (*loc. cit.*).

The chemicals used in this investigation were brought from Kahlbaum. The density of each solution was measured with a delicate chemical balance and a pycnometer. The refractive index of the polar liquids was measured by means of Abbe refractometer.

The experimental condenser was connected in parallel to the arm of the bridge containing the standard variable condenser. The change of capacity (dc) of the experimental condenser due to the introduction of the solution is determined from the readings on the standard condenser. Thus the *D.E.K.* of the solution is calculated from the relation,

$$\epsilon - 1 = \frac{dc}{C_0} = \frac{dc}{36.32} \quad \dots (5)$$

Results.

For each solution, C_1 and C_2 were calculated from the following relation:

If m_1 gm. of the polar liquid is dissolved in m_2 gm. of non-polar liquid, then

$$Z_1 = \frac{m_1}{M_1} \text{ and } Z_2 = \frac{m_2}{M_2}.$$

$$\therefore C_1 = \frac{Z_1}{Z_1 + Z_2} \text{ and } C_2 = \frac{Z_2}{Z_1 + Z_2}.$$

Knowing the value of ϵ from equation (5) P_{12} was calculated for each solution by equation (1).

For each mixture a graph was drawn showing the relation between C_1 and P_{12} . Then from the graph, $P_1 C_1$ was obtained by equation (2) and the values of P_1 at different concentrations were obtained by equation (3). Finally the values of P_1 were plotted against C_1 and the value of P_1 when C_1 is infinitesimal was thus obtained. Then by means of equation (4) the value of μ was evaluated.

TABLE I.

Substance	C_1	d_{12}	C_2	P_{12}
	0.00	0.872	2.26	26.50
	6.21	0.889	2.50	29.41
Methylene	15.62	0.936	2.95	33.30
chloride.	22.77	0.943	3.22	35.90
	29.73	0.968	3.49	37.53
	41.03	1.011	4.61	43.62
	0.00	0.872	2.26	26.50
	4.02	0.923	2.50	29.51
Methylene	7.50	0.961	2.63	31.20
bromide.	10.47	1.000	2.86	33.48
	13.98	1.046	3.05	35.50
	16.70	1.082	3.10	35.79
	19.50	1.121	3.21	39.06

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Substance.	C_1	d_{12}	C_2	P_{12}
	0 00	0 872	2 26	26 50
	2 97	0 983	2 47	29 50
Methylene iodide	9 62	1 064	3 09	36 52
	12 71	1 153	3 40	39 38
	14 75	1 192	3 55	40 87
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	0 00	0 872	2 26	26 50
	5 27	0 892	2 56	30 38
	9 50	0 902	2 81	33 46
Ethylidene chloride	12 40	0 914	3 13	36 62
	15 01	0 921	3 18	37 06
	21 30	0 938	3 67	41 40
	29 16	0 951	4 12	45 11
	34 34	0 965	4 95	49 00
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	0 00	0 872	2 26	26 50
	1 34	0 888	2 35	27 77
Ethylidene bromide.	3 40	0 915	2 53	30 18
	6 67	0 956	2 73	32 75
	0 03	0 985	2 95	35 14
	3 26	1 032	3 28	39 21
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	0 00	0 872	2 26	26 50
	0 81	0 891	2 30	27 50
Ethylidene iodide	1 70	0 941	2 58	29 90
	4 30	0 993	2 78	32 25
	6 70	1 045	2 95	34 56
	7 50	1 062	3 11	36 54

TABLE II

Chemical formula	n_1	d_1	P_1	P_1''	P_1'	$\mu \times 10^{18}$
CH_2Cl_2	1 425	1 378	70 0	15 78	54 22	1 61
CH_2Br_2	2 498	1 525	95 5	21 05	74 45	1 89
CH_2I_2	3 285	1 618	122 2	28 56	93 64	2 12
CH_3CHCl_2	1 417	1 180	100 0	21 08	78 92	1 95
CH_3CHBr_2	1 512	2 033	120 9	27 62	93 28	2 12
CH_3CHI_2	1 609	2 775	144 0	35 15	108 85	2 30

Discussion.

Williams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 1676) and others have noticed that benzene, though ordinarily considered to be non-polar, has an electric moment 0.06×10^{-18} C.G.S. electrostatic units. Hence our results are correct up to 0.06×10^{-18} .

The measurements on CH_2Cl_2 and CH_2Br_2 have also been repeated by this method to ensure correctness of the calibration and adjustment of the instrument. They agree remarkably well with the values obtained by the heterodyne method, thus :

	Mahanti and Sen-Gupta (<i>loc. cit.</i>).	Sanger (<i>Physikal. Z.</i> , 1926, 28, 556).
CH_2Cl_2	1.62×10^{-18}	1.59×10^{-18}
CH_2Br_2	1.91×10^{-18}	

The results presented in this paper further support the mechanism of the molecular model which was tentatively suggested in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*), *viz.*, that the CH_2Cl_2 molecule may be regarded as a distorted tetrahedron with the Cl-atoms at its two corners due to the interaction of the electronic orbits, the orbits of Cl-atoms as well as that of CH_2^{++} will be distorted. These distortions will develop moments in the two Cl-atoms as in the CH_2^{++} . The direction of the moment in the two Cl-atoms will be mutually inclined to each other and the moment of CH_2^{++} will be making equal angles with the direction of the moments in each Cl-atom. Treating now the electric moment as a vector quantity we can resolve the moments of the Cl-atoms and the net dipole moment of the molecule is the resultant of the moment of the CH_2^{++} and the resolved part of the moments of the atoms operating in the opposite direction. When Br is substituted for Cl, owing to larger nuclear charge of Br, they are mutually separated from each other to a large extent than in the case of Cl-atoms. This results in producing a net dipole moment larger than that of CH_2Cl_2 . Similarly the still larger value for CH_2I_2 can be explained. The values obtained in the case of ethylidene halides can be interpreted in a similar way. This view seems to have been supported recently by Willham (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 2350), and it may be also pointed out that in the first number of the new series of the *Annalen der Physik*,

Brüche has reviewed all the results obtained up to the present in getting an idea of the shape of the methane molecule and he suggested from his slow electron bombardment method that the structure of methane is perfectly symmetrical resembling an inert gas constitution similar to krypton and the addition of halogen ions produces the distortion of the structure as conceived in this paper.

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